

Health-Related Physical Fitness Variables and Students' Holistic Development

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to identify the relationship between health-related physical fitness variable to the holistic development of learners in St. John Parochial School in Tiaong, Quezon. The result shows that there is significant relationship between the student-respondents demographic profile and their holistic development. The student's age has a positive significant relationship with the emotional attributes. Likewise, positive significant relationship is depicted from student's grade level and their physical, social, and emotional attributes. Positive significant relationship is also present in the number of days students exercise to the physical and social attributes. However, there is no significant relationship present at student's gender and BMI to any of their holistic development. Furthermore, there is a positive significant relationship between the health-related physical fitness in terms of cardio-vascular endurance, strength, flexibility, balance, and coordination and student's holistic development in terms of physical, social, mental and emotional attributes.

KEYWORDS: health-related physical fitness, holistic development

INTRODUCTION

It is human nature that people engage in different kinds of activities that require the ability of the human body to perform certain movements needed in order to accomplish a task. In order to do such tasks, it is necessary that a person is physically fit so that the attainment of goals in each task will considerably be done in the easiest way possible.

In connection to this, schools offer a wide-range of activities and programs that will help students in developing themselves into a more performing individuals in terms tasks assigned to them. With that in mind, teachers expose students in different physical fitness activities to aid them in preparing them in dealing with activities related to their academics specifically in their Physical Education classes.

In the book of Corbin et. al. (2014) entitled *Fitness for Life*, they defined physical fitness as the ability of your body systems to work together efficiently to allow you to be healthy and perform activities of daily living. Furthermore, they also discussed that a fit person is able to perform schoolwork, meet home responsibilities, and still have enough energy to enjoy sport and other leisure activities.

Considering the abovementioned definition of physical fitness, it is evidently obvious that the fact that students can adhere and do all required activities in school and still has time to engage in different leisure activities means that they exemplified characteristics of being physically fit.

In addition, physical education is an inherent aspect of the educational process and a field of endeavor that attempts to produce physically, mentally, emotionally, and socially fit citizens through physical activities linked with a view to associated results (Khatun & Bandyopadhyay, 2016). It also improves students' health-related fitness, ability in movement activities, intellectual comprehension, and positive mindset through various physical exercises, allowing them to live a healthy and physically active lifestyle (Lobo et al., 2014a). Physical Education teachers and specialists are encouraged to revisit their teaching tactics and strategies to satisfy the students' demands effectively. However, early studies on students' knowledge of physical activities disputed and claimed that children thought physical education was crucial to their education (Tu et al., 2014a). Further, students' awareness of the necessity of physical activity is essential and significant to physical education for quality of life and well-being (Tannehill & Zakrajsek, 2018). According to Ghofrani and Golsanamlou (2017), Sistan and Baluchestan University students had a favorable attitude toward General Physical Education courses.

Through the different activities done in Physical Education classes, students then are being developed holistically making them equipped with skills needed not just in academics but also in real life's tasks. Holistic development refers to the overall growth of a

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person. Taking a holistic approach to education means focusing on all aspects of a child's growth, not just their academic advancements. Most importantly, it's about establishing the child's overall wellbeing (HEI Schools, 2022).

Looking through the global perspective of the study, it is identified that in order to enhance and nurture the holistic development of the students, school provides opportunities for students to participate in daily physical activity during the school day aside from the schedule PE classes. Meaning, in addition to PE classes and recess periods, teachers also provide regular physical activities integrated in different subject areas during the school days (Xue Zhao et. Al., 2021).

In the context of Philippine Education system, Department of Education has released DepEd Order No. 34 s. 2019, also known as the Revised Physical Fitness Test (PFT) Manual, which states that physical fitness is crucial for well-being and active life. The total progress of an individual should be prioritized in terms of the physical, mental, emotional, social aspects and health through a comprehensive physical fitness program and assessment. The learners can only perform at the height of their performance when they are healthy and strong. Thus, the learners need to actively engage in lifelong habits of regular physical activities for their overall health improvement and quality of life. Moreover, it was mentioned that PFT is a set of measures designed to determine a learner's level of physical fitness. It has two components Health Related and Skills Related Fitness.

Furthermore, DepEd CALABARZON (2021) also released a memorandum that promotes the enhancement of the students' welfare through participating in the different wellness activities in partnership with Nestle Philippines.

With the abovementioned information, this study aimed to assess the health-related physical fitness variable to the student's holistic development. Further, the findings of this study will serve as evidence and aid in improving activities in physical education classes so as to assure that physical activity and wellness needs of students will be met. Moreover, it will be advantageous not only to Junior High School students but also to those students enrolled in Physical Education classes.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to identify the relationship between health-related physical fitness variable to the holistic development of learners in St. John Parochial School in Tiaong, Quezon. Hence, the researcher sought to answer the following questions: (1) What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, grade level, frequency of exercise, and BMI? (2) To what extent do the respondent practice the following health-related physical fitness in terms of Cardio-Vascular Endurance, Strength, Flexibility, Balance, and Coordination? (3) How do the respondents perceive their holistic development in terms of Physical Attributes, Social Attributes, Mental Attributes, and Emotional Attributes? (4) Is there significant relationship between the students' demographic profile and perceived students' holistic development? and (5) Is there significant relationship between the health-related physical fitness variables and perceived students' holistic development?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This part dealt with the methods and procedures that the researcher will use in gathering the necessary data for the completion of the study. This included the research design, respondents of the study, sampling technique, research instrument, research procedures and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The researcher used descriptive method of research with the analysis of the relationship between manipulated variables and the development of generalization extending its conclusions beyond the sample observed. (Best and Kahn,1993)

Basically, this study is a descriptive correlational survey type. It involves investigations, which answer what was, and described the nature of the situation, as it existed and the time of study. It was also designed to estimate the extent to which different variables were related to one another in population of interest. (Padua et.al,1995)

The researcher also used descriptive correlational survey of research with is the suited method in testing the hypothesis of the study and to determine the Health-Related Physical Fitness Variable and Students Holistic Development.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were one hundred fifty-one (151) Junior High School teachers of St. John Parochial School. The respondents were divided according to their grade level. The table below showed the total number of respondents.

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents by Grade Level

GRADE LEVEL	POPULATION	SAMPLE
Grade 7	96	47
Grade 8	61	28
Grade 9	61	28
Grade 10	96	48
TOTAL	314	187

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The study involved students from Junior High School Department in the St. John Parochial School, Tiaong, Division of Quezon. Selected students were drawn using Slovin's Formula.

Sampling Techniques

The respondents were selected through systematic random sampling. This method of sampling was done by taking every k th element in the population, it applies to a group of individuals arranged in a waiting line or in a methodical manner (Priscillas S. Altares et al., 2003).

Research Instrument

The questionnaire was designed and used to gather large quantities of data from a diversity of respondents. It has several benefits over other forms of data collection in that it can be simply and quickly analyzed once completed, and was usually inexpensive.

In this study, the respondents accomplished a survey-questionnaire. Part I of the said research tool provided information profile of the respondents in terms of (1) name (optional); grade and section (optional); (3) age; (4) gender; (5) grade level; (6) parents monthly income; (7) gadget use in learning; (8) number of times exercising in a week; and (9) Body Mass Index (BMI).

Part II required responses pertaining to level of awareness and the extent of doing the basic health-related physical fitness in terms of: (1) cardiovascular endurance; (2) strength; (3) flexibility; (4) balance; and (5) coordination.

The researcher-made survey-questionnaire on physical fitness, which was based on the review of related literature and DepEd Order No. 34 s. 2019, "Revised Physical Fitness Test Manual", undergone validity and reliability testing. Face validity was determined by the researcher's thesis adviser, who determined whether or not the questionnaire items were related to the research problems. To assure content validity, the corrected questionnaire draft was given to two experts or professionals that were related to the field. Further, the content validity rating of all items must range from 1.70 to 2.00. It meant that all items in the questionnaire were relevant and covered the scope of the research being conducted on the knowledge of the junior high school students towards the basics of physical exercise and activities after the transition to the new normal.

Part III was an adapted instrument from Salimi, Moh et. al., 2020, The Profile of Students' Skills Bengawan Solo Nature School, European Journal of Education Research V.10, Issue 1, 211 – 226, that required responses pertaining to the students' capability to do the following students holistic development: (1) physical attributes; (2) social attributes; (3) mental attributes; and (4) emotional attributes.

To test the reliability of the instrument, pilot testing was conducted. Twenty-five (25) students in other Junior High Schools that were not included in the study was selected to answer the items in the questionnaire. After three days, copies of the questionnaire were retrieved from the pilot testing respondents. Once the value or responses in each item fit to the required Cronbach alpha value, the survey questionnaire can be distributed to the main respondents. If the value did not fit to the required number, the researcher will give another set of revised researcher-made survey questionnaires to the same pilot testing respondents. Using Cronbach alpha, the reliability test result should be 0.70 or above, which means that the research instrument is reliable enough to be distributed as a final survey questionnaire.

Research Procedure

The data were collected through survey-questionnaires that followed a descriptive-quantitative research design. The researcher prepared a hardcopy questionnaire for face-to-face data gathering and an online survey-questionnaire using Google Forms and administered them to the respondents through email and online platforms such as Facebook Messenger, etc. The responses of each respondent were collected, tallied, and tabulated for the interpretation of the results.

Ethical considerations were necessary for research projects. Each participant received a consent letter explaining some of the key elements of the study and what was expected of them as participants. A consent form that was reviewed by the Research Ethics Committee at Quezon Medical Center (QMC) will be attached to the letter, which participants will sign if they agree to take part and understand their participation in the study. All of the information gathered was kept confidential and used only for this research study and for compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. As soon as the data that was gathered is presented, analyzed, and interpreted, all responses will be permanently deleted to prevent other people from accessing all the personal information. Only the researcher will have access to the responses in the survey.

Statistical Treatment of Data

For sub problem 1, the data collected about the profile of the selected Junior High School Students were described with the use of frequency and weighted mean.

For sub problem 2, the data on the responses of the respondents about the extent of practices health-related physical fitness were described with the use of weighted mean.

For sub problem 3, the data on the responses pertaining to the students' capability to do the following students' holistic development were treated using weighted mean.

For sub problem 4, the data concerning the relationship between the profile of the respondents and perceived students' holistic development were treated using Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient.

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For sub problem 5, the data concerning the relationship between the health-related physical fitness variables and perceived students' holistic development were also treated using Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient.

The following range scores were used in the interpretation of the relationship of the variables:

Size of Correlation	Interpretation
.90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00)	Very high positive (negative) correlation
.70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90)	High positive (negative) correlation
.50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70)	Moderate positive (negative) correlation
.30 to .50 (-.30 to -.50)	Low positive (negative) correlation
.00 to .30 (.00 to -.30)	Negligible correlation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter includes the tables which present the data of the findings in this study with their respective interpretations. The data were analyzed and interpreted, so that conclusions and recommendations can be drawn from the result of the study.

Table 2. Students' Demographic Profile

A. Age Bracket	Number of Respondents
12-13	79
14-15	70
16-17	1
B. Gender	Number of Respondents
Male	42
Female	73
LGBTQIA+	34
Prefer not to Say	1
C. Grade Level	Number of Respondents
Grade 7	34
Grade 8	23
Grade 9	37
Grade 10	56
D. Days of Exercise	Number of Respondents
0-1	28
2-3	51
4-5	46
6-7	25
E. Basic Mass Index	Number of Respondents
Underweight	13
Normal	114
Overweight	8
Obese	15

Table 2 shows the distribution of the respondents based on their demographic profile. Part A presents the distribution according to their age and most of the respondents are at age 12 years old – 13 years old. The distribution consists of seventy-nine (79) or 52% 12 – 13 years old, seventy (70) or 47% 14 – 15 years old, and only two (2) or 1% are 16 – 17 years old.

Part B shows the distribution of the respondents according to their gender and most of the respondents are female. The distribution consists of seventy-three (73) or 48% female, forty-two (42) or 28% male, thirty-four (34) or 23% LGBTQIA+ and only one (1) or 1% prefer not to say.

Part C shows the distribution of the respondents according to their grade level and most of the respondents are from Grade 10. It also consists of fifty-six (56) or 38% Grade 10, thirty-seven (37) or 24% Grade 9, thirty-four (34) or 23% Grade 7 and also twenty-three (23) or 15% are Grade 8.

Part D shows the distribution of the respondents according to the frequency of exercise and most of the respondents exercise 2 – 3 days in a week. It also consists of fifty-one (51) or 34%, forty-six (47) or 31% 4 – 5 days, twenty-eight (28) or 18% 0 – 1 day and only twenty-five (25) or 17% are 6 - 7 days.

Part E shows the distribution of the respondents according to their Body Mass Index (BMI) and most of the respondents are normal. It also consists of one hundred fourteen (114) or 76% normal, fifteen (15) or 10% obese, thirteen (13) or 9% underweight and only eight (8) or 5% are overweight.

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Table 3. Summary of the Extent of Student Respondents in their Health-Related Physical Fitness

INDICATORS	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Cardio-Vascular Endurance	2.21	0.75	Practice
Strength	2.17	0.84	Practice
Flexibility	2.23	0.81	Practice
Balance	2.24	0.85	Practice
Coordination	1.95	0.83	Moderately Practice
OVERALL	2.16	0.82	Practice

Table 3 summarizes the extent of student-respondents exposure to their health-related physical fitness.

The overall mean of 2.16 interpreted as “practice” summarizes that student-respondents are exposed to the different health-related physical fitness variables.

This simply presents that the respondents actually have the basics of these physical fitness variables since these are usually done whenever they have their Physical Education classes where they are being exposed and prepared to do different kind of activities that require exertion of effort and body movements.

The highest mean is the balance with 2.24 interpreted “practice”, flexibility is 2.23 interpreted also as “practice”, followed by cardio-vascular endurance 2.21 interpreted “practice” and strength with 2.17 and interpreted as “practice”. On the other hand, coordination is the lowest mean of 1.95 which is interpreted as “moderately practice”.

Table 4. Summary of the Perceived Student-Respondents Holistic Development

INDICATORS	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Physical Attributes	2.86	0.79	Manifested
Social Attributes	3.25	0.63	Highly Manifested
Mental Attributes	3.19	0.70	Manifested
Emotional Attributes	3.29	0.66	Highly Manifested
OVERALL	3.15	0.70	Highly Manifested

Table 4 summarizes the perceived student-respondents holistic development in terms of their emotional attributes

The overall mean of 3.15 interpreted as “highly manifested” summarizes that student-respondents exhibits the holistic development.

It is evident in the result of the survey that the respondents can gauge their emotional attributes and are aware of the different scenarios or instances that can be a part of the process of developing one’s emotional state.

The highest mean is the emotional attributes with 3.29 interpreted “highly manifested”, social attributes is 3.25 interpreted also as “highly manifested” and followed by mental attributes 3.19 and interpreted “highly manifested”. On the other hand, physical attributes are the lowest mean of 2.86 which is interpreted also as “manifested”.

Table 5. Relationship between the Student-Respondents Demographic Profile and their Holistic Development

Demographic Profile	Physical Attributes	Social Attributes	Mental Attributes	Emotional Attributes
Age	0.005	0.117	0.138	.181*
Gender	0.003	0.032	0.035	0.061
Grade Level	.245**	.236**	0.154	.291**
Frequency of Exercise	.375**	.174*	0.038	0.102
BMI	0.017	0.042	-0.011	-0.061

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

As shown in the table 5, there is significant relationship between the student-respondents demographic profile and their holistic development. The student’s age has a positive significant relationship with the emotional attributes. Likewise, positive significant relationship is depicted from student’s grade level and their physical, social, and emotional attributes. Positive significant relationship is also present in the number of days students exercise to the physical and social attributes. However, there is no significant relationship present at student’s gender and BMI to any of their holistic development.

It can be inferred on the result that the demographic profile of the respondents greatly contributes to the total human development. This means that as the student-respondents age, they acquire different learnings and information that they can use to provide meaning to their lives as well as to generalize the importance of a thing in one’s lives and its existence. These learnings that they gained from experience then shaped them as individuals in all aspects of lives as to the different attributes presented in this study.

Table 6. Relationship between the Health-Related Physical Fitness and Students' Holistic Development

Demographic Profile	Physical Attributes	Social Attributes	Mental Attributes	Emotional Attributes
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cardio-Vascular Endurance	.463**	.268**	.238**	.277**
Strength	.548**	.301**	.298**	.287**
flexibility	.559**	.230**	.208*	.251**
balance	.517**	.314**	.240**	.329**
coordination	.550**	.302**	.203*	.257**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Gleaned clearly in table 6 that there is a positive significant relationship between the health-related physical fitness and student's holistic development.

Since health-related physical fitness activities cater almost all senses of an individual's, the extent of how a person involves himself in different forms of exercise contributes a great portion in the total human development or holistic development of an individual. These means that even though the activities being performed by the respondents are designed to make them healthy, it does not only make the person physically healthy but also enhances and improves other life aspects of a person like emotional well-being and sense of being sociable.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

On the basis of the earlier findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the students' demographic profile and their perceived holistic development is rejected.
2. The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the health-related physical fitness variables and the perceived students' holistic development is rejected.

Based on the findings and conclusions made, the following are recommended:

1. Junior High School Students. Engage themselves more in different physical fitness activities so that they can develop healthy habits maintaining their body in shape and making them holistically developed so that they can perform well in their everyday living.
2. MAPEH Teachers. Conduct of trainings and workshops aligned with proper execution of drills for physical fitness to teachers so that they will be able to impart the correct way of performing such activities to students, in turn making the students informed of not just the concepts but also its application.
3. School Administration. Schools must develop a well-planned and well-organized program that will further hone students' holistic development through various activities inculcated in the said program.
4. Department of Education. Modification to the current curriculum being utilized by the agency is suggested where additional content on holistic development and physical fitness would be highlighted as part of the aim to inform and orient learners on its importance.
5. Future Researchers. Further researches relevant to the subject matter should be done to fully prove the significant findings and fill in gaps identified in the conduct of this study

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